

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: RAUM****FIRST NAME: DOMINIQUE****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA**

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Commented [GK1]: Note that in UK English which you opted to use, personal and degree titles are not punctuated

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The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2019, Grammarly v.1.0.23.343 and Zotero v.6.0.19 on Windows 10

1. Introduction
2. Steps to creating an essay (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 6-14)
3. The difference in languages (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 33-39)
5. The used style (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 40-42)
6. Abbreviations (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 58-64)
7. Conclusion

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BASICS OF PAPER WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Starting a new study at a university is always a challenge and a journey in itself. It is even more when you address the academic level of a postgraduate PhD. Rules are to be followed strictly when writing scientific papers. Those rules differ between sciences, universities, editors, etc. What restrictions are to be followed at [Euclid University](#) is the subject of this first course, named ACA-401D. It may seem an insurmountable challenge for foreigners to learn the English language, but it can be mastered when studying the lesson attentively. Hereafter are some main ideas given in the first period.

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2) STEPS TO CREATING AN ESSAY

Writing a scientific paper or essay only goes with preparation ahead of the actual writing. Several steps must be followed to prepare your paper in the best way possible. As Cleenewerck and Gulma described 20021 in their work "ACA-401/ACA-401D", there are seven steps in academic essay writing: Starting the essay, researching the topic, organising your ideas, writing the essay, referencing the essay, editing the essay and [handling](#) in the essay.

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a) Starting the essay

When beginning with the establishment of an essay, the writer should start as early as possible to be able to manage his time. The scientific question being defined, the writer needs to access everything he knows about the subject to be able to answer his starting question. Creating a roadmap for the essay will enable him to follow the steps toward a conclusion. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7–8)

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b) Researching the topic

Being able to develop a thesis needs research on the topic. You need to build up your knowledge to apport evidence. Before reading books, papers, articles or whatever source you are going to use, you should ask yourself four critical questions: “What do I already know about the topic? What do I need to read and know to write the essay? Is this material useful to my topic/argument? Can I use this material to support my answer?”. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021)

c) Organizing your ideas

Once the research on the subject is done, you need to organise your thoughts, structure your work and create a plan for your writing. A helpful guide is determining the possible result of your thesis and collecting the information needed for evidence. The sketch of those points will represent your plan. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 10–11)

d) Writing the essay

Drafting is an important step. As you have started working on the essay on time, you can, and should, stretch the establishment of your work over several days following the simple three steps structured format of an introduction at the beginning, the main body in the middle and a conclusion at the end. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 10)

e) Referencing the essay

All scientific work is at risk of becoming an illegal copy of someone others work. While copying statements are not forbidden, they must be marked as such and referenced. The referencing method is subject to changes in style depending on the establishment you are writing for. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 11)

f) Editing the essay

As stated under section d), you should have time to re-read your work and edit it. Changes to your essay may be made after several days, adding or improving your arguments and statements. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 11)

g) Handing in the essay

As obvious as it seems, handing in your essay is the last step in creating a paper. As such, it is essential to follow the given directives regarding the deadline and the form of the paper. It is necessary to meet the requirements. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 12)

3) THE DIFFERENCES IN LANGUAGES

English has become the world's most important language as it is the most common language to be spoken worldwide (Wikipedia 2023). Nevertheless, there are variations to this language, mainly American and British English. While the sounding of the variation in English may seem obvious when heard, the differences also affect the spelling and grammar, the meaning, the usage of different parts of a sentence (for example, nouns or adjectives), the everyday use of the language, the jargon, and so on. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 24–32)

4) PLAGIARISM

As already mentioned in section e), copying another author's work is allowed as long as it is referenced as being that author's work. Failing to do so will result in plagiarism. There are several situations when you have to cite the author: "When using any quote, paraphrase, statistic/data, or visual (such as a graph) that is borrowed from another source". (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34)

5) THE USED STYLE

As the writing of an essay starts, the writer needs to follow not only the rules of the language used, in the case of this paper, it would be British English rules, but also the style of the paper as demanded by the institution the document is being written for. EUCLID University provides a template to use by students depending on what form they have to deliver. Following this template, the student will have to follow the requirements of the demanded style of citations, as there are many different ones. The most commonly used style is the Turabian style, named after its creator. Using style sheets will enable to create a unified presentation of papers inside an establishment and provide guidance to the paper's author. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 40–42)

6) ABBREVIATIONS

Other than commonly used, abbreviations should not be used in the main text. "They are not used outside parentheses". (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 40) Using abbreviations

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that are not commonly used (for example, e.g. or etc.), you should “give the full term on first reference, followed by the abbreviation in parentheses”. (Turabian 2018, 353)

7) CONCLUSION

Writing a paper may seem difficult regarding the rules and requirements one has to follow. Luckily, style sheets are often provided by the establishment you write for when you have to follow a specific structure. Choosing the citation style for your work will enable you to use programs that help keep track of your references. Additional programs may assist you in your writing with the grammar and spelling of a selected language. Both would be used while editing your paper before handing it in. [Euclid University provides](#) the student with all the luggage he needs through the course pack, videos, [and books, as](#) well as access to some handy programs.

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Turabian Kate L. 2018. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th edition. Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.